

FRENCH ROMANTICISM

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Annotation: this article is written about romanticism and its history, its place in French literature, writers who created in the direction of romanticism and their classification in works of art.

Keywords: romanticism, currents, era, lyrics, historical novel, drama, style, history.

French romanticism developed in the first thirty years of the 19th century. Its initial stage dates back to the period of the consulate and the first empire (1801-1815). At this time, romantic aesthetics were formed only by the first writers of the new direction: Chateaubriand, Germaine de Stael, Benjamin Constant. The second stage began during the restoration period (1815-1830), when the Napoleonic empire disintegrated in France and the Kings of the Bourbons dynasty returned. During this period, a romantic school is finally formed, all genres of romantic literature appear and flourish: lyrics, historical novel, drama; 71 major romantic writers: Lamartin, Nerval, A. de Vigni, Hugo. The third stage is the years of the July Monarchy (1830-1848), the first Republican uprisings, the spread of the ideas of utopian socialism. Romantics face new social challenges, resulting in the romantic social novel genre (George Sand). French romanticism emerged among aristocratic emigrants as an attitude towards the French Revolution and the Enlightenment associated with it. The first romantics poeticized the feudal past. Their work was pessimistic. Indeed, the 19th century cannot be imagined without Hugo. Moreover, his work predetermined the development of not only French, but also European literature for the next decades. Victor Hugo (1802-1885) son of General count Hugo, governor of three provinces. He and his older brothers (Abel and Eugene) were talented and wonderful. Victor learned to read early. At the age of seven, he was able to translate Virgil and Tacitus. In 1811, mother Sophie About him in September 1817, he critically said: "I am fifteen years old, poorly written, I could write better"; and then: "the stupid things I did before I was born." But it is difficult not to be surprised by the greatness of Hugo's talent and hard work, because the notebook consisted of thousands of poems, a comic opera, a prose melodrama by Inessa de Castro, a five-act tragedy called "Atalia" or "Scandinavia". Epic "flood". And Hugo painted all these works with his own hands![1: 71] during the same period, he would be prepared to enter the Polytechnic School after attending Louis The Great College. He could only write poetry at night. In 1817, the French Academy published a selection of poems on the topic "happiness that teaches a person in any conditions." Hugo took part in this competition and took ninth place among famous poets. Renuar then said, "If it is true that he has become so old, the Academy should encourage the young poet." At a public meeting, an excerpt from Hugo's work was read. The ladies applauded the boy. Hugo was delighted. The newspapers immediately showed interest in the miracle boy. Even then, Victor said: "I want to be a Shatobriand or nothing." At the age of

sixteen, Victor writes the poem "My farewell to childhood": what happened this time? Or rather, what happened to me? I look like a tired madman, and a vain mind is looking for itself... O glory, Almighty genius, give your Singers a place in the distance, kind; to you-all thoughts and goals; so allow my verses to reach you. Sophie Hugo firmly believed that her children would become great writers. In 1819, Victor won the first prize for winning the poetry competition in Toulouse. He even defeated Lamartin, who was ten years older than him. Now they are talking about Hugo in Paris. From 1819 to 1821, Victor and his brother Eugene Literary Conservative A committee was formed to study historical monuments. Lamartine said of this book: "this is a huge work, an antediluvian block. This is Shakespeare in the novel, this is a medieval epic; but this temple has everything you want, only there is no religion in it. "A huge work" - this is how everything that comes out of the pen of Victor Hugo can be described. These are the trilogy "The Legend of the ages" (1856-1859), the novels "The Poor" (1840-1870), "The Laughing Man" (1869), "the ninety-third year" (1872-1873); poetic collections: "autumn leaves" (1831), "dark songs" (1835), "inner voices" (1837), "contemplations" (1853), "light and shadows" (1840), "revenge" (1852-1853), "songs of streets and Forests" (1865), "the art of being a grandfather" (1877); poems: "Olympic grief" (1840), "the power of things" (1853), "imperial dress" (1853), "the end of Satan" (1855), "God" (1855) and infinite number of essays, articles, numerous correspondence. Hugo was a true broadcaster of the time. In 1881, Hugo's birthday was celebrated as a national holiday: a triumphal arch was installed on Eilau Avenue in his honor; Hugo himself was greeted with a parade. On the day of the funeral, two million people walked after the Hugo coffin. 12 young French poets lined up in the guard of Honor. Everywhere - on the streets, in houses-around the triumphal arch, where thousands of people read his poems in tune; verses, verses and separate words were heard, such as rustling. For the first time in the history of mankind, the people paid tribute to the poet, until that moment it was given only to sovereigns and military leaders. "Yes, he, Hugo, was a master," concludes Maurois, "a connoisseur of the French word, but he had another brighter title - a connoisseur of human feelings. He sang better than others what everyone had experienced: the grief that the motherland honors its sons, the joy of the young father, the charm of childhood, the happiness of first love, everyone's duty to the poor, the horror of defeat. and and the greatness of mercy. In fact, expressing one's time in such a deep and touching way is a great gift.

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